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D12.2 Report from VITALISE platform access and usage

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package

Abstract

This document "D12.2 - Report from VITALISE platform access and usage" provides an overview of the VITALISE project's Virtual Access (VA) platform, detailing its usage, user interaction, and feedback.

The report begins by outlining the sources of data for analysis, primarily sourced from the Discovery Portal (DP) and the EU Survey questionnaire tool. Methods for analysis include examining published datasets, registered users, RAI Nodes activity, experiments, and post-VA questionnaires.

Results show that the VA attracted 159 registered users, with datasets spanning various categories. Analysis of user interaction reveals typical lifecycle patterns, peaking during user training and outreach campaigns.

System Usability Scale (SUS) results suggest room for improvement, with an average score of 68.27. However, overall impressions of the VA are positive, reflecting the project's commitment to open science and FAIR principles. Feedback suggests areas for enhancement, such as improving dataset quality and implementing a ranking system.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are reviewed, indicating satisfaction with the tool, researchers' willingness to share data, and interest in future collaborations. Despite successful VA usage, participants have yet to produce results, but express readiness to share findings.

In conclusion, the VITALISE VA platform demonstrates promising engagement among researchers, highlighting areas for improvement to enhance user experience and promote collaboration in open science initiatives.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP12

In Work Package 12 (WP12) of the VITALISE Project, our focus lies on facilitating seamless access to the datasets collected during the Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and Transnational Access (TAs). Our mission is not only to grant access to them but also to ensure the secure management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) and the acknowledgment of researchers' contributions, respecting regulations for personal and sensitive data.

Our primary objective is to enable researchers to explore and utilize the diverse datasets generated within the project, by establishing clear access policies, allowing for flexible data sharing while upholding security and privacy standards. Virtual Access will be granted to researchers who applied, without any selection criteria. Subsequent submission of analysis summaries and publications allows us to monitor the quality of work and assess the effectiveness of Virtual Access.

In essence, Work Package 12 serves as the gateway to a pool of data generated with the VITALISE project, enabling researchers to access and use them for research in the health and wellbeing domain, while safeguarding the integrity and security of valuable information. This experience will not only provide proof of the value of the research generated by the project, but it will also prove as a viable service for future exploitation of the research infrastructures. To this end, Living Labs will be able to support their Research Infrastructures' operations by safely sharing data, engaging in open science approaches and promoting the living lab models for experimental research to the science community at large and the health and wellbeing communities in particular.

1.2.1 Applicable KPIs

There are Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined which the VITALISE project strides to accomplish. Some of the defined KPIs provide important context to WP12, and the decisions explained in this document:

1. **KPI1.2: Number of Total Researchers Recruited for Virtual Access:** this is the main metric that is being tracked.
2. **KPI2.1: Different Types of Datasets:** Diversifying the range of datasets available within the VITALISE platform encourages researchers to register and perform more and better research.

3. **KPI2.2: Qualitative Measures of Researcher Satisfaction with Datasets:** The satisfaction of researchers engaging in Virtual Access activities is collected, the comprehensive feedback mechanisms and satisfaction surveys, qualitative data on researchers' experiences with the datasets is reported.
4. **KPI5.2: Satisfaction of Researchers to Process Data Online Rather Than Download and Process the Datasets on Their Computers:** The usage of Discovery Portal's feature to run experiments on Datasets is reported.
5. **KPI6.1: Willingness of Researchers to Share Their Data for Processing Through the VITALISE Platform:** On the data producers' side, VA needs to engage data owners to share their data, by enabling safe and easy platform to do so.

1.3 About this deliverable

This deliverable is D12.2 named "Report from VITALISE platform access and usage"; includes statistics on the access provided to researchers. This deliverable will provide descriptions of the source of data, statistics on the data registered as accessible for VA, statistics on users' registration, their interaction with the VITALISE VA platform as well as statistics on the generated synthetic data, executed experiments and any exploitation of the produced results by the external researchers.

2 Analytical Methods

As a short introduction to the analysis of VA, the sources and methodology of analysis are described to better understand the results presented in section 3.

2.1 Sources of data

There are fundamentally 2 sources of data: data provided by the Discovery Portal (DP) and Data collected through the EU Survey questionnaire tool.

Figure 2.1 Screenshot of the Discovery Portal dashboard feature, as an example, data displayed is relative to 6/4/2024 not the final data. It is also shown how DP data is exported in different formats from this interface.

The DP provides an overall dashboard to monitor activities, status, and metrics of the VA. It also provides the functionality to export data in different formats:

- Metadata: Dataset ID, title, description, Author, Host RAI node and Type
- Registered Organizations: Name, Website, address, Research Background, Country, #applicants, Project description and duration. This table contains the results of the registration questionnaire.
- Registered Users: ID, Name, last name, email address, Organization, Position, and ORCID (if any). This table represents all registered users who can access the DP (including administrators and VITALISE Consortium members).
- Logs: DP’s internal auditing of all transactions including timestamp, event type, User ID and any further details which include important parameters for the different event types. These logs were carefully designed and requested through requirements to WP3 (this process is described in D12.1). This is the fundamental source of information to report on temporal series of data as it provides 2061 events from 27/11/2023 till 11/04/2024.

The EU Survey tool is used to manage the Post-VA questionnaires/reports/impressions sent to VA participants on the last phase of VA. This questionnaire is explained in D12.1, includes:

- Socio-Demographic information for profiling,
- the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire,
- some open questions about the impressions,
- the Net Promoter Score (NPS) question,
- and finally some questions about the research the participants are engaged with which substitute a final report.

2.2 Methods

Considering the items collected for the VA datasets, different analytical techniques can be implemented to extract insights. The dimensions of the analysis follow a logical segmentation considering both KPIs and system architecture as well as all necessary dimensions to contextualize these. Dimensions include:

1. **Published datasets:** This analysis is necessary for testing the hypothesis that the more datasets there are, the more diverse they are (KPI2.1), the more quality they have and the more entries each has more probable it is to attract CA participants.
2. **Registered Users:** The number of users is not only a KPI (KPI1.2) for the project, it drives the VA experience itself, as VA is for the users to benefit. Number of users would also provide statistical significance to the results.
3. **RAI Nodes:** These are key infrastructures provided by the VITALISE consortium. Especially for the RAI Nodes, as they host the datasets, they are the backbone for accessing them through the DP. The RAI Nodes are also responsible of executing experiments.
4. **Experiments:** This is one of the key features of VA, alongside access. VA Participants can execute data experiments over synthetic or real data in a safe and private way. This dimension is important as part of the KPI5.2.
5. **POST-VA:** The questionnaire which collects organizations and users' types, impressions, usability and reports of VA work. This dimension is important for measuring satisfaction with the datasets (KPI2.2).
6. **Published Research:** as part of the DoA WP12 is monitoring the results of VA in terms of publications.

Throughout the report, time analysis is used to provide insight into progression patterns. The data is grouped by week, therefore the week-in-year number is used to identify the periods. Collected data on VA starts on week 48 of 2023 (27 Nov 2023) and ends on week 15 of 2024 (14 Apr 2024).

For the **published datasets for VA**, the final set is presented with basic statistics including frequency of access and detection of peak usage times. Data is visualized using time-series charts, showing trends over time. Additionally, access patterns are analysed using heat maps to highlight which datasets are the most popular.

Registration data is evaluated using content analysis to categorize and quantify the types of information provided by users. In this sense, we analyse the different professions that have accessed the VA, the different countries they come from, the age range, gender, education level and area of expertise of each user. This information allow us to better understand the demographics and professional backgrounds of the VITALISE VA participants. Descriptive statistics and user behaviour analysis is performed by quantifying the total number of users. In addition, cluster analysis to segment users based on their activity patterns such as logins, accessing dataset information, downloading datasets and requesting experiments is graphed. A Day of the week/Hour heatmap of user activity has been created to give us more insights on the users' behaviour.

RAI Nodes will report an aggregated activity (including their own registration, any Dataset operations, and experiments) per week per node. This allows the analysis of activities per node, contextualizing dimensions such as datasets interactions or experiments execution.

Experiments requests are analysed per user (considering only active users using this feature), analysing the frequency and time of experiment requests. Additionally, a heatmap analysis by RAI Node provides justification for the need for the proliferation (or not) of RAI Nodes).

Considering the questionnaire after the use of VA (**Post-VA questionnaires/reports/impressions**), the analysis of System Usability Scale (SUS) was carried out first. The SUS generates a quantifiable measure called the SUS score¹, which ranges from 0 to 100 and offers information about overall customer satisfaction and usability. A higher score indicates improved usability, whereas a lower score indicates possible usability issues. To perform this analysis the [System Usability Scale toolkit](#) available in GitHub will be used. Reports about the personal evaluation after the use of the VITALISE VA and the impression involve coding the data into themes and patterns, manually turning them into graphs or using Large Language Models and Word Clouds, to observe those that are most recurrent.

In order to analyse the **published papers**, a systematic review methodology is applied to find any paper related to VITALISE and the Virtual Access which has not be authored by VITALISE consortium members. Since we suspect that participants may have not been completed any publications to date, *in the future*, a bibliometric analysis of the published papers could be performed to assess the impact and reach of the VA experience in academic literature. Citation analysis could help track how many times articles have been cited, which would indicate their influence.

3 Results

This section reports the results of the VA analysis. The results are divided into Datasets, Users, RAI Nodes, Experiments, and finally the

3.1 Published Datasets

In this section we present details and statistics of the published datasets, like which have been published, which types they are, when where they published, and how many times where each accessed.

3.1.1 Final set

Table 1 Final list of published datasets.

Title	Author(s)	RAI Node	Type
Aging and wellbeing - EQ5D3L	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - Sociodemo	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - Sociodemo	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - SPQ	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - UCLA	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant

¹ [https://www.questionpro.com/blog/system-usability-scale/#:~:text=The%20System%20Usability%20Scale%20\(SUS\)%20is%20a%20questionnaire%20that%20i,s,systems%2C%20whether%20software%20or%20hardware.](https://www.questionpro.com/blog/system-usability-scale/#:~:text=The%20System%20Usability%20Scale%20(SUS)%20is%20a%20questionnaire%20that%20i,s,systems%2C%20whether%20software%20or%20hardware.)

Title	Author(s)	RAI Node	Type
Aging and wellbeing - UCLA	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - UTAUT	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Aging and wellbeing - UTAUT	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
Anonymised Body Weight and Fat Ratio (Withings Data Test)	Author	VICOM	Anonymised
Body Weight and Fast Ratio (Withings Data Test)	Author	VICOM	Non Anonymised
COVID-X cough dataset - users stats	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
COVID-X cough dataset - wavefiles	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
Debugging Listener	JungleHippo	AUTH	Anonymised
GameBus reinforcement schedules monetary incentives - 1a-intervention-data	TUE - Raoul Nuijten, Pieter Van Gorp	VICOM	Non Data Model Compliant
GameBus reinforcement schedules monetary incentives - 1b-pre-test-survey-data	TUE - Raoul Nuijten, Pieter Van Gorp	VICOM	Non Data Model Compliant
GameBus reinforcement schedules monetary incentives - 1c-post-test-survey-data	TUE - Raoul Nuijten, Pieter Van Gorp	VICOM	Non Data Model Compliant
GameBus reinforcement schedules monetary incentives - 1d-monetary-incentives-data	TUE - Raoul Nuijten, Pieter Van Gorp	VICOM	Non Data Model Compliant
JRA3 - Setting the path for the future Grador Active Tool	INTRAS	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
LifeSpace - Transitional Access	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
LifeSpace - Transitional Care Device RAW	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant
LifeSpace - Transitional Care Responses	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Non Data Model Compliant

Title	Author(s)	RAI Node	Type
Non Anonymised Body Weight and Fat Ratio (Withings Data Test)	Author	AUTH	Non Anonymised
Older adults and technological innovations	Thomas More - LiCalab - University of Stavanger	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
Physical training In-Game metrics for cognitive assessment: Evidence from extended trials with the FitForAll exergaming platform	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
Physiological_Data_Subject1	Author	VICOM	Anonymised
Senior balance test	Laurea University of Applied Sciences & Mikko Julin	AUTH	Non Data Model Compliant
Streamlit Dataset	Mikel	VICOM	Anonymised
Withings Scale Measurements - Fat Ratio - example array	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Anonymised
Withings-data	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	AUTH	Anonymised

There are a total of 42 published datasets, which is a substantial increase from the 13 initial set. Some of those datasets (especially the anonymised ones) are testing datasets generated by AUTH to check the plugin development (i.e. connecting data as VDMC dataset). Table 1 shows the filtered list of published datasets. Figure 3.1 shows some statistics.

Figure 3.1 Distribution of Datasets by hosting RAI Node and type

3.1.2 Publishing progression

Figure 3.2 Dataset publication progression per week (2023-2024)

When a dataset is created, a log event “metadata creation” is added to the DP’s Log. Similarly, when the dataset is modified and deleted.

The graph shows there is a testing phase of the later weeks of 2023; a heavy creation phase on early 2024; and a correction week on the 10th and 12th weeks of 2024 which represent the curation of datasets and correction of datasets from the initial feedback.

3.1.3 Popular Datasets

Table 2 Heatmap of Dataset Access and downloads per week (2023-2024)

Name	51	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Aging and ... - EQ5D3L	3	4	1		2						1	3	3			
Aging and... - Sociodemo													3			
Aging and ... - Sociodemo													2			
Aging and wellbeing - SPQ	2	10			1		1				1	5	2			
Aging and wellbeing - UCLA																
Aging and wellbeing - UCLA													1			
Aging and ... - UTAUT													4	1		
Aging and ... - UTAUT	1	4				1					1	4	6			
Anonymised Body Weight ...				1						2	1	1	2			
Body Weight and Fast Ratio				3			2				1	4	1			
COVID- ... - users stats																
COVID- ... - wavefiles																
Debugging Listener			2									1	1		1	
GameBus (...) - 1a-interventi										5	4	4	6	1		
GameBus (...) - 1b-pre-test-										1	2	1	1	1	1	
GameBus (...) - 1c-post-test-										2		1	3	1		

Name	51	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
GameBus (...) - 1d-monetary										3	1	1	3	1		
JRA3 - ... Gradior Active Tool	4	2			2	3	2			1	1	3		4		
LifeSpace - TA			3				1				2	2	9	1		
LifeSpace - TC Device RAW			2		1							1	5	4		
LifeSpace - TC Responses												1	4	1		
Non Anonymised Body Wi...							1			1		1	4			
Older adults and technol...	3	5			5		1				2	9	3	5		
Physical training In-Game ..																
Physiological_Data_Subject 1											1	1	4	1		
Senior balance test	1	2	1				1		2	3	4	9	23	10	2	
Withings Scale Measureme...			1			3				2	2	5	8		1	
Withings-data		3	3	1	1	1				2	1	6	4	5	3	1

3.2 Registered users

Figure 3.3 User Registration and logins progression

All users, including internal (personnel from VITALISE consortium), could still interact with the platform. After filtering some invalid users (reported in the monthly reports) the total number of registered users which is 159.

3.2.1 Sociodemographic analysis

Table 3 presents the demographic characteristics of the 14 study participants. The predominant range of age is 30-40 years old (7/14, 50%) with the majority of the participants being male (9/14, 64.29%) and possessing a Master's degree or higher (10/14, 71.43%).

Table 3 Participants characteristics

Characteristics	N	%
Age distribution, n (%)		
20 - 30	3	21.43 %
30 - 40	7	50.00 %
40 - 50	3	21.43 %
50 - 60	1	7.14 %
60+	0	0 %
Gender, n (%)		
Female	5	35.71 %
Male	9	64.29 %
Other	0	0 %
Unknown	0	0 %
Education, n (%)		
ISCED 0: Early childhood education	0	0 %
ISCED 1: Primary education	0	0 %
ISCED 2: Lower secondary education	0	0 %
ISCED 3: Upper secondary education	1	7.14 %
ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education	0	0 %
ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education	0	0 %
ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level	3	21.43 %
ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level	4	28.58 %
ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level	6	42.85 %
Country, n (%)		
Belgium	1	7.14 %
Spain	6	42.86 %
Greece	4	28.58 %
The Netherlands	1	7.14 %
Italy	1	7.14 %
Austria	1	7.14 %

Figure illustrates the primary characteristics of the socio-demographic data gathered.

Figure 3.4 Socio-demographic distributions

3.2.2 User interaction

Because most of the activities within the Discovery Portal are logged, we can track the overall user experience. Figure represents the number of logs per week for the different types of user activities tracked, which are login, accessing metadata, downloading a dataset, and requesting an experiment over a specific dataset. All follow a pattern where there is an early peak of usage in week 2 of 2024 and a more intense period peaking on the 12th week of 2024. During this period a new recruitment campaign was launched, particularly centred in developer partners of members of the consortium (for VA dissemination campaigns details see D13.5).

The data shows that for every login there is on average 1,65 accesses to metadata; which corroborates the fact that users browse the datasets every time they login. There are 0.19 data downloads for every login, meaning that a user, on average, logs in 5 times before downloading data. There are 0.27 experiment requests per user login, meaning that, an experiment is requested on average after 3 or 4 sessions in the platform.

Figure 3.5 User Engagement data per week (login, access, download, experiment)

Figure 3.6 Frequency of total activity per user

In order to also corroborate that the VA was used for research we can look at the heat map of activity by time of day and day in week. Table 4 shows that much of the user activity is performed during the work hours this is 7-16 Monday thru Friday; since the time is GTM, these times correspond to 8-15 in CET and 9-16 in EET which are the most common countries of access (see D12.1 for countries of registered users).

Table 4 Day of the week/Hour heatmap of any user activity.

DoW	0	1-5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
Mon			2	82	20	18	24	14	24	51	18	13	17	1	0	2	1	4	0	
Tue			4	13	20	40	43	24	23	40	65	64	29	11	1	0	13	2	1	
Wed			2	29	30	34	74	84	48	23	55	35	9	1	0	0	4	0	2	
Thu			2	8	33	47	64	58	36	32	109	46	54	1	0	1	5	1	2	

Fri	1		2	10	19	18	45	50	89	59	6	94	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sat			0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sun			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	0

3.3 RAI Nodes

RAI Nodes host datasets, generate synthetic data and run requested experiments. VITALISE architecture has this component which allows research infrastructures to retain their data on their premises while sharing only metadata, synthetic data or digital experiment results. Figure 3.7 presents the RAI Node activity per week per node. This indicates which RAI nodes are more active and when.

Figure 3.7 RAI Node activity (Registration, Dataset lifecycle and experiments) per Node and week

3.4 Experiments

There have been a total of 135 Experiment requests throughout the VA period. These requests have been requested by 18 users (11% out of the total valid users). There are a couple of “power users” who request experiments throughout the period, there are “early adopters” who test the feature very early (week 2-4); while most of the users apparently request experiments in week 12 (or later).

Table 5 Heat map of experiment requests by user each week

UID	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
225cb11a			1							4	1	1		
78f57f5a	3	5			14	8	5	12	1	20	8	15	1	
f6ecbad5											3			
ee47bd4d	1													
23bd36c2			10											

UID	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
c19d4fce											1			
b66b6a1c											1			
bb0021fe											3			
775a6cdc											3			
0f8d9e83											1			
4c4ea99c											4			
9f5fc47e											1			
f753dcbd											1			
b58c9662											1			
c8f99dff											2			1
562692d2											1			
db06dbad												1		
ab5fc931													1	

These experiments were executed in RAI nodes which host the dataset over which the experiment should be executed. Table 6, reports on the RAI node experiment requests by node per week.

Table 6 Time series analysis of experiments requested per RAI per week

RAI	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
AUTH		5	1		8	1	2	4		19	28	17	2	
VICOM	4						1	7	1	3	2			1
UPM			11		6	7	2	1		2	1			

3.5 Post-VA reports and impressions

In this section we will summarize the 14 responses from VA participants of the questionnaire sent to VA participants on the last phase of VA.

3.5.1 System Usability Scale results

Presenting the results using [System Usability Scale toolkit](#)'s single variable (only one system study).

Figure 3.8 Single Variable Analysis as reported by System Usability Toolkit

According to the box plot on the left hand side of Figure 3.8, the median score is 70, which is the middle value when all scores are arranged in order. The IQR, which spans approximately from 60 to 80, indicates that the middle 50% of scores fall within this range. This suggests moderate variability in how users rated the system's usability. Given that the median SUS score is around 70 and considering the categories on the usability rating scale, the VA usability can be classified as “OK” to “Good”. This suggests that users found the VA system somewhat satisfactory but not outstanding. Taking into account the questionnaire (Bottom of the figure): Question 5 - I found the various functions in the product were well integrated: Has the highest percentage of "Agree" responses, indicating that most participants were favorable toward what this question assessed. Question 10 - I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this product: Displays a significant "Neutral" to "Agree" shift, suggesting mixed but generally favorable responses. Question 2 - I found the product unnecessarily complex: Shows a notable amount of disagreement, with 23% of participants disagreeing or strongly disagreeing. As a global result, the VA is rated as a category C.

Table 7 Interpretation data as reported by System Usability Toolkit

SUS Study Score: 68.27	
Median	70
Standard Dev.	19.57
Adjective	OK
Grade	C
Acceptability	Marginal
Quartile	2nd

3.5.2 Virtual Access Impressions

When asked about expectations of VA, participants were quite conscious about the goals of VA. The participants had expectations of accessing high-quality datasets for research, exploring different databases easily, having easy options for sharing data, and finding datasets relevant to their research. They anticipated enhanced access to ready-to-use datasets, ease of use, and support for FAIR data management principles.

Figure 3.9 Word cloud of the open answers to the question: "What kind of expectations did you have concerning your Virtual Access?"

When asked how well the expectations were met, the participants' responses varied, with some expressing satisfaction that their expectations were met, while others felt that the platform fell short in terms of dataset size or relevance to their research. Overall, opinions leaned toward a positive assessment, with some suggesting room for improvement in the future.

Figure 3.10 word cloud of the open answers to the question: "How well were your expectations regarding the Virtual Access met?"

Figure 3.11 impressions on online processing and usefulness

Participants appreciated various aspects of the Virtual Access platform, including its commitment to open science and ethical considerations, the availability of multiple health-related datasets, its ease of use and well-structured instructions, and the simplicity of the user interface. Additionally, some valued its contribution to effective research and adherence to data management best practices.

Figure 3.12 word cloud of the open answers to the question: "What did you appreciate most about the Virtual Access?"

Figure 3.13 Net Promoter Score, or willingness to recommend the tool with others

3.5.3 Virtual Access Report

Participants engaged in various activities related to the Virtual Access platform, including sharing datasets, conducting general analysis, familiarizing themselves with the platform through test activities, accessing health-related datasets for medical device improvement, testing dataset uploads, and evaluating the platform's capability for future dataset uploads and secondary data uses. Some participants also registered, logged in, discovered datasets, used filters, and downloaded datasets or experiment templates.

Participants described a variety of contexts for their research, including dataset curation and analysis for different European-funded projects, development of smart home rehabilitation tools for post-stroke hand rehabilitation, testing purposes, private company research, involvement in the VITALISE research project, PhD theses and research projects, participation in a Horizon-funded project, exploration of available data, and gathering transdisciplinary knowledge for developing an innovative screening system for dementia.

Participants aimed to achieve various objectives related to the Virtual Access, including expanding accessibility to data, obtaining data on existing hand-related performance metrics for stroke patients, accessing health-related data for testing purposes, and utilizing enhanced datasets for further analytics, particularly in the context of children and adolescent obesity prevention. Additionally, objectives included finding relevant data for specific projects, evaluating the platform's capability for future dataset uploads and secondary data uses, focusing on FAIR Data Management, and detecting the emotional state of palliative care patients using voice recognition processing methods.

Figure 3.14 Word cloud of the description of objectives of VA applied to participants' research

Participants utilized various datasets and services during their Virtual Access, including accessing metadata for almost all datasets, multiple datasets for testing purposes, datasets related to older adults, data downloading services, and specific datasets such as "Body Weight and Fat Ratio (Withings Data Test)." Additionally, some participants explored synthetic data and other available data sources to inspire future use of the platform for their specific research aims, particularly in improving psychosocial support for palliative care patients and enhancing their emotional well-being and quality of life.

Participants utilized various methodologies to leverage the datasets, services, technologies, and tools available through the Virtual Access platform for their research projects. These methodologies included analysing metadata with AI to make general statements and extracting statistical information from datasets. Some participants used existing datasets to validate or disprove hypotheses related to hand use time in stroke patients and improve reported performance measures. Others engaged in exploratory data analysis or performed calculations on the data. Additionally, some participants planned to continue training and refining their models using available datasets to improve robustness in future research. Finally, there were intentions to utilize datasets to enhance interventions for palliative care patients, aiming to improve psychosocial support and enhance emotional well-being and quality of life.

Figure 3.15 Word cloud of the description of the Methodology of VA related research activities

Participants reported various outcomes from their use of the Virtual Access platform, although most (71%) indicated that they had not yet achieved results or had not utilized the platform extensively. Some responses indicated that the data accessed was useful, while others mentioned finding useful results without providing specific details. One participant highlighted the platform as a promising tool for accessing datasets and analytical tools, with the potential for future use as it is scaled up. Additionally, there were responses indicating that no results were available yet or that the platform had not been extensively used to generate findings.

Participants provided a range of recommendations for the Virtual Access platform in relation to their research. These included suggestions for providing more extensive and voluminous datasets, active support in anonymizing datasets, and the introduction of additional weight monitoring data for obesity studies. One participant recommended implementing a ranking system to highlight datasets generating the most interest, thereby fostering increased engagement with sought-after data. Additionally, some participants indicated that they did not have specific recommendations at the time.

Participants outlined various channels for disseminating the results of their research, including publications in JCR indexed journals, articles, workshops, and LinkedIn. Some participants mentioned plans for publications, while others indicated a focus on understanding how to use the platform for future research steps without immediate plans for dissemination.

Not all participants found the question about the willingness to share results relevant to them, only half answered, out of which most were encouraged to share their results in different levels of intent as shown by Figure .

Figure 3.16 Willingness to share results. Blue: Discouraged, Red: interested but blocked; Green: Encouraged

Most participants indicated no interest in commercializing the research results. Some expressed interest in potential returns on investment in data gathering and sharing in the future. Additionally, one participant highlighted the importance of fostering a community of users and ensuring research integrity before considering commercialization.

Published papers & Research networks

While performing a systematic review of papers mentioning VITALISE project (i.e. containing terms such as “VITALISE”, “Virtual Access”, or “grant agreement 101007990”; Filtering out articles authored by members of the consortium, and non-relevant papers), we found no publications from external researchers.

This could be due to the short time since the VA experience, or to the fact that researchers have not acknowledged VITALISE as instructed by the terms and conditions. Using ORCID, which 51 registered users declared a valid ORCID (one of which is duplicate), we searched for their latest publications. There were no publications implying the use of VA datasets in the time period where VA is executed.

4 Conclusions

The Virtual Access (VA) platform, an integral component of the VITALISE project, is revolutionizing research accessibility through its innovative integration with the Discovery Portal (DP). VA empowers researchers with access to diverse datasets. This section provides a comprehensive overview of VA’s inception, objectives, methodology, and key findings.

It is important to report the calendar dates of important events of the VA and particularly DP:

Table 8 VA Calendar

Date	Description
28/11/2023	Official VA launch
11/01/2024	Virtual Access (VA) RAI System Webinar
08/02/2024 to 14/02/2024	Migration to the RCS new version deployed by WITA: testing the new deployment and system integration so the number of interactions was probably up during this period
19/03/2024	Second round of VA promotion

The utilization of the Discovery Portal (DP) generated logs allowed for the streamlined creation of periodic reports, which were then easily reviewed by the expert panel.

Despite the limited response rate, with only 14 participants completing the questionnaire, representing approximately 10% of the total, valuable insights were still gleaned from their feedback.

Throughout the duration of the project, a total of 42 datasets were eventually published across the three RAI Nodes, demonstrating a substantial catalogue of datasets offered. Analysis revealed that a majority of the datasets (57%) were categorized as NDM (Non VITALISE Data Model compatible), underscoring the importance of ongoing curation efforts to offer more VDMC (VITALISE Data Model Compliant) datasets which might also be more interesting for researchers since these usually register device data, and this is a popular dataset topic (more below). Interestingly, most datasets were published early on, predominantly in Week 2 of the project timeline, indicating an early and active engagement with the platform, coinciding as well with the webinar of the RAI System. The curation of datasets emerged as a critical aspect, with notable removals occurring in Weeks 10 and 12, coinciding with significant spikes in user activity. However, it's worth noting that other factors may have influenced this surge in registrations.

Among the datasets, "Senior Balance Test" emerged as the most popular, balancing quality and relevance to researchers' interests effectively. Datasets containing data collected from devices and questionnaire results garnered considerable interest, whereas those labelled as "test" datasets were perceived as less valuable, potentially signalling their platform validation nature rather than experimental results.

User registration followed an expected trajectory, with notable spikes coinciding with DP webinars designed for internal use, indicating their effectiveness in attracting researchers to publish datasets.

Demographically, the mean VA participant was identified as a highly educated individual in their 30s to 40s, predominantly male, and from Spain. While gender equality remains an issue, underlying factors may contribute to this skew. The majority of VA participants held advanced degrees (master's or doctorate), aligning with the target population of professional researchers and suggesting a successful outreach campaign.

Analysis of user interaction patterns revealed a typical lifecycle per user, characterized by registration, login, dataset browsing, and engagement in experiments, mostly during work hours, indicating professional or educational usage. Temporal analysis highlighted two significant periods of high activity: early on during user training (Week 2) and later during the main outreach campaign (Week 12). Periods of low activity corresponded to vacation periods.

The activity patterns of RAI Nodes mirrored user engagement, with peaks aligning with aforementioned user activity pattern and a proportional level of activity relative to hosted datasets.

Experiment request patterns revealed a few power users, notably the VITALISE platform development team and early adopters from consortium partners, with a concentration of requests during the peak activity in Week 12.

SUS results yielded an average score of 68.27, indicating room for improvement but offering valuable feedback for future iterations to enhance user experience.

Overall, impressions of the VA were positive, aligning with the overarching goals of the VITALISE project and its commitment to open science and FAIR principles. Feedback highlighted areas for improvement, such as enhancing the quality of the dataset catalogue and implementing a ranking system. Despite the success of VA, participants have yet to produce any results yet from VA, however they are indeed interested in sharing these results.

Finally, to conclude, let's review the relevant KPIs which have been discussed in this deliverable.

KPI1.2: Number of Total Researchers Recruited for Virtual Access: a total of 159 registered users are certified.

KPI2.1: Different Types of Datasets: There are 8 topic categories of datasets, as well as 3 categories of types of datasets.

KPI2.2: Qualitative Measures of Researcher Satisfaction with Datasets: Average satisfaction with the tool is 4 out of 5; on average each dataset was downloaded 9.1 times; 18 users requested and average of 7.5 experiments.

KPI5.2: Satisfaction of Researchers to Process Data Online Rather Than Download and Process the Datasets on Their Computers: When asked Users expressed favourable satisfaction with experiment feature, averaging 4 out of 5.

KPI6.1: Willingness of Researchers to Share Their Data for Processing Through the VITALISE Platform: All VITALISE research infrastructures published at least one dataset; VA participants share the conviction of Open Science and showed interest in sharing any results with the platform or through publications. Out of the 13 VA participants who delivered VA final Report, 6 reported this question did not apply to their research, and only one explicitly responded negative willingness to share; thus 86% where willing to share results.

Appendices

Appendix 1. January 2024 Report

Virtual Access Services and Usage Statistics

Available Datasets

Available datasets to access increased in 62 to a total of 85 by the end of the period. The next graph represents the cumulative number of available datasets each week of the period.

Next available datasets are shown by hosted RAI NODE and type.

Dataset Access

The next table shows the frequency with which datasets are being accessed each week.

Name	1	2	3	4
20240115_test-manj_binary			1	
Aging and ... - EQ5D3L	4	1		2
Aging and wellbeing - SPQ	10			1

Name	1	2	3	4
Aging and ... - UTAUT	4			
Anonymised Body Weight ...			1	
Body Weight and Fast Ratio			3	
Debugging Listener		1		
Debugging Listener		2		
JRA3 - ... Gradior Active Tool	2			2
LifeSpace - TA		3		
LifeSpace - TC Device RAW		2		1
Older adults and technol...	5			5
Senior balance test	2	1		
Streamlit Dataset		1		
test_fitbit_bin_rasp			1	
test_listener_bin_rasp			1	
test_withings_bin_rasp2			1	
Withings Scale Measureme...		1		
Withings-data	3	3	1	1

The next graph shows accumulated number of dataset access by dataset type.

User Engagement and activity

Registered users increased in 22 to a total of 24 by the end of the period. The next figure shows different metrics of user engagement such as registration of users, how many datasets are downloaded (NDM download), how many experiments are requested, and how many datasets are uploaded (metadata create); all represented in cumulative number per week.

Representing the user activity, the next graph shows how many times have there been user logons, and how many times there was a consultation about a particular dataset (metadata access, not necessarily implying the user downloaded it)

The next graph represents individual user activity in the period. All activities for all users have been counted, this is the total activity count per user represented in the horizontal axis; the number of users with the same activity count is the vertical axis. As example, an activity count of 1 is a user *either* “registering” or “logging in”; an activity count of 2 is a user “registering and logging in” or “logging in and querying a dataset”.

RAI Node activity

The next graph represents the accumulated total activity per RAI node. This activity includes Creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests.

Virtual Access services' assessment report

This section presents the Virtual Access services' assessment report, produced by the VA international expert's board. The assessment report is based on the Virtual Access services' report (Section 1), produced by the VITALISE consortium. The board is composed of 2 independent members (Dimitri Schuurman and Gareth Priday) coming from the harmonization board, who have already been introduced to the project and were already engaged with it, and 1 member from the consortium (Teemu Santonen from Laurea partner).

Teemu Santonen: Teemu Santonen received his Ph.D. (Econ.) degree in Information Systems Science from Aalto University in Finland in 2005. Currently he is acting as a "Knowledge Intensive Business Services (KIBS)" principal lecturer at the Laurea University of Applied Sciences in Finland. Prior his academic career Santonen was working over a decade as a consult and a development manager in leading Finnish financial, media and ICT sector organizations. Santonen is also a scientific panel member of International Society of Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM) and is former board member of Finnish Strategic Management Society. In Laurea Santonen has been leading Service Design and co-creation research program. Currently he is managing co-creation and business development activities for three major EU-funded project having a total budget over 10 MEUR and including 41 partners across Europe. The Finnish Inventor Support Association have honored Santonen's novel crowdsourcing based open innovation platform as the best school related innovation in Finland. As of today he has published over 60 scientific papers. His current research interest focuses on "Open Innovation management", "Living labs in context of health/wellbeing and circular economy", and "Social Network Analysis (SNA)".

Dimitri Schuurman: As program manager Roadmapping & Living Labs, Dimitri Schuurman is responsible for strategic innovation management in the AI & Data department at imec. He holds a PhD in innovation management in Living Labs from Ghent University (UGent) and the Free University of Brussels (VUB) in Belgium. Together with his imec colleagues, Dimitri developed a specific Innovation Management methodology with supporting innovation canvasses (under the label 'Innovatrix'), specifically designed for multi-stakeholder and multidisciplinary innovation projects. He also leads a special interest group on Living Labs in the International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM) and is active in the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) as a Living Labs specialist. His main interests and research topics are in the areas of open innovation, user innovation and innovation management.

Gareth Priday: Gareth Priday is a director of the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network (ALLIN) and is an active practitioner with the Future Self Living Lab hosted by Swinburne University. He is a foresight practitioner with Action Foresight, most recently supporting an 18-nation forum on developing a 2050 strategy. In addition, he is a director at Ethical Fields, which specialises in

community wealth building and regenerative business models. He has over a decade of experience facilitating workshops that provide exploration and activation contexts for long term thinking, leadership, strategy, innovation, and organisational dynamics. He holds a Master of Strategic Foresight. His first career was in the financial services sector, working with many large international banks in the UK and Australia.

Available datasets

There is an increase in the number of available datasets as the consortium keeps uploading datasets to be available for virtual access. As the Virtual Access in VITALISE is provided through distributed nodes, there seems to be a balance on the datasets hosted by the nodes of AUTH and VICOM while those hosted in UPM's node are fewer. It is interesting that the majority of those hosted in AUTH's node are following the VITALISE data model, while the majority in the other 2 nodes are Non Data Model Compliant. This allows for more flexibility to the researchers but decreases the levels of findability.

Data set access

The report shows a clear interest of external researchers to datasets dealing with Aging and wellbeing as well as ageing and technology. The datasets that contain assessment based on standard questionnaires (EQ5D3L, SPQ, UTAUT) seem to be accessed more. There is also interest in datasets that follow well established formats, such as Withings data. This could be attribute to the fact that researchers feel more comfortable to access data that they already know their value and how to use. As anticipated, given the fact that VITALISE designed the "VITALISE Data Model" which is not a standard yet, the external researchers showed a strong preference for Non Data Model Compliant datasets. For instance, Withings data model does not follow "VITALISE Data Model". It would require extra effort from the data owner (partner from the consortium) to transform it to VITALISE data model as well as from the external researcher to use the VITALISE data model when s/he was familiar with the Withings data model.

User Engagement and activity

Only 24 users had registered by the end of the period, but this could be justified by the fact that it is the 1st month of virtual access. On the other hand, the report show that there are returning users as the number of user logins is about 4 times higher than the number of users while the number of metadata access (browsing datasets) reached more than 250. Based on the report, half of the users performed at least 2 activities in the system. The experiments execution is around 25, while the number of Non Data Model datasets download is close to 50 which can be translated to 1 experiment execution for every 2 datasets downloads.

RAI Node activity

AUTH's node had the most activity in terms of creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests. This is just resources management as it does not affect the experience of external researchers who access any node through a unified portal.

Dimitri Schuurman

Gareth Priday

Teemu Santonen

Appendix 2. February 2024 Report

Virtual Access Services and Usage Statistics

Available Datasets

Available datasets to access decreased by 2 to a total of 83 by the end of the period.

Next available datasets are shown by hosted RAI NODE and type.

Dataset Access

The next table shows the frequency with which datasets are being accessed each week.

Name	5	6	7	8	9
Aging and wellbeing - SPQ		1			
Aging and ... - UTAUT	1				
Anonymised Body Weight ...					2
Body Weight and Fast Ratio		2			
GameBus (...) - 1a-interventi					5
GameBus (...) - 1b-pre-test-					1

Name	5	6	7	8	9
GameBus (...) - 1c-post-test-					2
GameBus (...) - 1d-monetary					3
JRA3 - ... Grador Active Tool	3	2			1
LifeSpace - TA		1			
Non Anonymised Body Wi...		1			1
Older adults and technol...		1			
Senior balance test		1		2	3
Withings Scale Measureme...	3				2
Withings-data	1				2

The next graph shows accumulated number of dataset access by dataset type.

User Engagement and activity

Registered users increased in 22 to a total of 46 by the end of the period. The next figure shows different metrics of user engagement such as registration of users, how many datasets are downloaded (NDM download), how many experiments are requested, and how many datasets are uploaded (metadata create); all represented in cumulative number per week.

Representing the user activity, the next graph shows how many times have there been user logons, and how many times there was a consultation about a particular dataset (metadata access, not necessarily implying the user downloaded it)

The next graph represents individual user activity in the period. All activities for all users have been counted, this is the total activity count per user represented in the horizontal axis; the number of users with the same activity count is the vertical axis. As example, an activity count of 1 is a user *either* “registering” or “logging in”; an activity count of 2 is a user “registering and logging in” or “logging in and querying a dataset”.

RAI Node activity

The next graph represents the accumulated total activity per RAI node. This activity includes Creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests.

Virtual Access services' assessment report

This section presents the Virtual Access services' assessment report, produced by the VA international expert's board. The assessment report is based on the Virtual Access services' report (Section 1), produced by the VITALISE consortium. The board is composed of 2 independent members (Dimitri Schuurman and Gareth Priday) coming from the harmonization board, who have already been introduced to the project and were already engaged with it, and 1 member from the consortium (Teemu Santonen from Laurea partner).

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Gareth Priday: Gareth Priday is a director of the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network (ALLIN) and is an active practitioner with the Future Self Living Lab hosted by Swinburne University. He is a foresight practitioner with Action Foresight, most recently supporting an 18-nation forum on developing a 2050 strategy. In addition, he is a director at Ethical Fields, which specialises in community wealth building and regenerative business models. He has over a decade of experience facilitating workshops that provide exploration and activation contexts for long term thinking, leadership, strategy, innovation, and organisational dynamics. He holds a Master of Strategic Foresight. His first career was in the financial services sector, working with many large international banks in the UK and Australia.

Available datasets

The number of available datasets decreased by 2 compared to the previous report. The balance of datasets hosted by the nodes of AUTH and VICOM still exists while those hosted in UPM's node are fewer. Similarly to the previous report, the majority of those hosted in AUTH's node are following the VITALISE data model, while the majority in the other 2 nodes are Non Data Model Compliant. This allows for more flexibility to the researchers but decreases the levels of findability.

Data set access

Withings is still among the preferred dataset, but there is a shift of interest towards datasets produced by software applications developed by partners of the consortium during past projects, such as Grador from INTRAS and GameBus from TUE. The most popular dataset for this period is again a dataset produced by a validated assessment test, the Senior Balance Test. This could be attributed

to the fact that researchers feel more comfortable to access data that they already know their value and how to use. As anticipated from the previous report and given the fact that VITALISE designed the “VITALISE Data Model” which is not a standard yet, the external researchers showed a strong preference for Non Data Model Compliant datasets.

User Engagement and activity

The number of registered users was doubled, reaching 46. The number of users' logins and dataset browsing proves that there are many returning users. Almost half of the new users performed at least 2 activities. During this period, the ratio between experiments execution and Non Data Model datasets download is close to 1. This means that for each NDM dataset download, an experiment is executed.

RAI Node activity

For this report, AUTH's and VICOM's node had balanced activity in terms of creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests. This is just resources management as it does not affect the experience of external researchers who access any node through a unified portal.

Dimitri Schuurman

Gareth Priday

Teemu Santonen

Appendix 3. March 2024 Report

Virtual Access Services and Usage Statistics

Available Datasets

Available datasets to access decreased by 48 to a total of 35 by the end of the period. This decrease is due to an intense curation process, cleaning testing, temporary and otherwise overruled datasets.

Next available datasets are shown by hosted RAI NODE and type.

Dataset Access

The next table shows the frequency with which datasets are being accessed each week.

Name	10	11	12	13
20240115_test-manj_binary	1			
20240115_test-manj_binary			1	1
Aging and ... - EQ5D3L		1	3	3
Aging and... - Sociodemo				3

Name	10	11	12	13
Aging and ... - Sociodemo				2
Aging and wellbeing - SPQ		1	5	2
Aging and wellbeing - UCLA				1
Aging and ... - UTAUT				4
Aging and ... - UTAUT		1	4	6
Anonymised Body Weight ...	1	1	2	
Body Weight and Fast Ratio		1	4	1
Debugging Listener				1
Debugging Listener		1	1	
GameBus (...) - 1a-interventi	4	4	6	1
GameBus (...) - 1b-pre-test-	2	1	1	1
GameBus (...) - 1c-post-test-		1	3	1
GameBus (...) - 1d-monetary	1	1	3	1
JRA3 - ... Gradior Active Tool	1	3		4
LifeSpace - TA	2	2	9	1
LifeSpace - TC Device RAW		1	5	4
LifeSpace - TC Responses		1	4	1
Non Anonymised Body Wi...		1	4	
Older adults and technol...	2	9	3	5
Physiological_Data_Subject1	1	1	4	1
Senior balance test	4	9	23	10
Streamlit Dataset		1		2
test_fitbit_bin_rasp			1	1
test_listener_bin_rasp	1			
test_listener_bin_rasp2			1	1
test-withings		2	3	1
Withings Scale Measureme...	2	5	8	
Withings_testing_20231116	2	1		1
Withings-data	1	6	4	5

The next graph shows accumulated number of dataset access by dataset type.

User Engagement and activity

Registered users increased in 117 to a total of 163 by the end of the period. The next figure shows different metrics of user engagement such as registration of users, how many datasets are downloaded (NDM download), how many experiments are requested, and how many datasets are uploaded (metadata create); all represented in cumulative number per week.

Representing the user activity, the next graph shows how many times have there been user logons, and how many times there was a consultation about a particular dataset (metadata access, not necessarily implying the user downloaded it)

The next graph represents individual user activity in the period. All activities for all users have been counted, this is the total activity count per user represented in the horizontal axis; the number of users with the same activity count is the vertical axis. As example, an activity count of 1 is a user either “registering” or “logging in”; an activity count of 2 is a user “registering and logging in” or “logging in and querying a dataset”.

RAI Node activity

The next graph represents the accumulated total activity per RAI node. This activity includes Creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests.

Virtual Access services' assessment report

This section presents the Virtual Access services' assessment report, produced by the VA international expert's board. The assessment report is based on the Virtual Access services' report (Section 1), produced by the VITALISE consortium. The board is composed of 2 independent members (Dimitri Schuurman and Gareth Priday) coming from the harmonization board, who have already been introduced to the project and were already engaged with it, and 1 member from the consortium (Teemu Santonen from Laurea partner).

Teemu Santonen: Teemu Santonen received his Ph.D. (Econ.) degree in Information Systems Science from Aalto University in Finland in 2005. Currently he is acting as a "Knowledge Intensive Business Services (KIBS)" principal lecturer at the Laurea University of Applied Sciences in Finland. Prior his academic career Santonen was working over a decade as a consult and a development manager in leading Finnish financial, media and ICT sector organizations. Santonen is also a scientific panel member of International Society of Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM) and is former board member of Finnish Strategic Management Society. In Laurea Santonen has been leading Service Design and co-creation research program. Currently he is managing co-creation and business development activities for three major EU-funded project having a total budget over 10 MEUR and including 41 partners across Europe. The Finnish Inventor Support Association have honored Santonen's novel crowdsourcing based open innovation platform as the best school related innovation in Finland. As of today he has publish over 60 scientific paper. His current research interest focuses on "Open Innovation management", "Living labs in context of health/wellbeing and circular economy", and "Social Network Analysis (SNA)".

Dimitri Schuurman: Dimitri Schuurman leads the Business & Domain Expertise Center at imec's Digital Transformation Department focussing on the domains Sustainable & Urban Environments, Mobility & Logistics and Public Health & Nutrition. In his role, he is responsible for all living lab and innovation methodologies and also for measuring trends and impacts in the context of wiked problems. He holds a PhD on Living Lab organizations and methodologies from Ghent University & the Free University of Brussels in Belgium. Together with his imec colleagues, Dimitri developed a specific Innovation Management approach & framework (called Innovatrix) which is specifically designed for multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary innovation projects. He also leads a Special Interest Group on Living Labs in the International Society for Professional Innovation Management (ISPIM) and is active in the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) as a Living Labs specialist.

His main interests and research topics are situated in the domains of open innovation, user innovation and innovation management.

Gareth Priday: Gareth Priday is a director of the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network (ALLIN) and is an active practitioner with the Future Self Living Lab hosted by Swinburne University. He is a foresight practitioner with Action Foresight, most recently supporting an 18-nation forum on developing a 2050 strategy. In addition, he is a director at Ethical Fields, which specialises in community wealth building and regenerative business models. He has over a decade of experience facilitating workshops that provide exploration and activation contexts for long term thinking, leadership, strategy, innovation, and organisational dynamics. He holds a Master of Strategic Foresight. His first career was in the financial services sector, working with many large international banks in the UK and Australia.

Available datasets

During the last period, the total number of available datasets decreased to 35. Based on the report, this decrease is due to an intense curation process, cleaning testing, temporary and otherwise overruled datasets. There is a balance of the datasets hosted among the 3 nodes (AUTH, VICOM and UPM). There is also a balance between the Non Data Model Compliant and the VITALISE Data Model datasets which means that there was an increase on ratio between the 2 types of datasets.

Data set access

In this period, there is a significant increase in dataset access. More datasets are access by the external users. Following the previous periods' findings, the most popular datasets are those produced by validated assessment tests. To this end, the Senior Balance Test was the dataset access more, followed by those applying standard assessment tools to older adults and Withings. The datasets produced by GameBus and Grador are accessed more than the average, following the previous report findings while datasets produced by LifeSpace living lab have been discriminated. As far as the preference on the data model type, the Non-Data Model Compliant dataset were accessed more.

User Engagement and activity

The total number of users increased to 163. The target number was set at 200, given that two of the three years were during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is pleasing to see that over 80% of the target was hit. The number of users login reach 400 while the number of dataset browsing was higher than 800. This is the first time, compared to the previous reports, that the number of experiments execution is higher than the datasets downloads. This could be attributed to the face that researchers that had download a sample dataset once, processed it more times by using VITALISE RAI nodes. And this is the value of the VITALISE Virtual Access platform. That external users can process datasets without having to download them. There is a clear increase in number of external users that perform more than 2 activities in the platform, compared to the previous periods.

RAI Node activity

Following the increase number of datasets in the RAI node of UPM, the node's activity (creating, modifying or deleting datasets, as well as experiment requests) has been almost equally distributed among the 3 nodes. This is just resources management as it does not affect the experience of external researchers who access any node through a unified portal.

Dimitri Schuurman

Gareth Priday

Teemu Santonen